

MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF OLIVE KERNEL GASIFICATION IN A 2 MW_{TH} BFB GASIFIER

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ABSTRACT: Gasification is a promising and attractive thermochemical method for biomass-to-energy conversion. Fluidized bed gasifier is one of the best options for large scale operation. In the present work, olive kernel biomass fuel was gasified in a 2MW_{th} air blown, atmospheric, fluidized-bed gasifier, located at CENER's facilities in Navarra Spain. In order to facilitate the operation of the gasification power plant, a process model based on the Aspen Plus[®] simulation software was developed. Both experimental and simulation studies set light on the basic operating parameters, such as temperature, mass flow rates of material streams, and syngas composition during the air-blown gasification of olive kernel in the gasifier. Uncertainties related to discontinuous feeding of biomass, temperature variation and simulation assumptions led to deviations between the experimental and simulation results.

Keywords: Olive kernel, Gasification power plant, ABFB reactor, Process simulation

1 INTRODUCTION

The increase of renewables share in gross energy consumption and the adoption of the circular economy principles through innovative and efficient processes constitute important measures to achieve clean energy transition. Biomass is a cheap and widely-distributed renewable energy source with a neutral carbon footprint. Bioenergy potential in EU is estimated to contribute with 140 Mtoe to the Gross Final Energy Consumption (GFEC) in 2022. For the target year of 2030, bioenergy could reach values between 160 and 180 Mtoe, representing a share around 15 % of the GFEC. In particular, Greece possesses a high biomass potential (23 Mt), with agricultural residues (e.g., olive/grapevine prunings, olive kernel) amounting at approximately 50 % (Figures 1, 2).

Figure 1: Annual quantity of agricultural residues in Greece

Figure 2: Annual quantity of agro/industrial residues in Greece

In specific, Greece represents the third largest olive oil industry worldwide with an annual capacity of approximately 450,000 tons of olive kernel (OK) waste [1]. Spain is the second largest olive oil industry with an average annual production of 1.5 Mtons of olive oil (Fig. 3). As a consequence, olive residues possess a great share among other agro/industrial residues with an annual quantity of c.a. 9.5 Mtons for the year 2020 (Fig. 3)

Figure 3: Annual production of olive oil and olive residues in Spain

Biomass gasification takes place at high temperatures (600 to 1000 °C) and atmospheric pressure by employing several gasifying agents (i.e., air or pure oxygen or/and steam or/and CO₂), resulting in a gas mixture containing mainly H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and traces of light hydrocarbons. Syngas from biomass gasification can then be utilized either as fuel in Internal Combustion Engines, gas turbines or even in high temperature solid oxide fuel cells or as raw material for the production of Fischer-Tropsch synthetic liquid fuels and value-added chemicals [2]. In the present work, the operation of a 2 MW_{th} gasification power plant with olive kernel biomass fuel is presented. A model in Aspen Plus for olive kernel gasification is applied in order to compare the simulation and the experimental results obtained from the 2 MW_{th} gasifier operating at CENER facilities, specifically in Biorefinery and BioEnergy Centre (<https://www.bio2c.es>) placed in Aoz (Spain). The comparison focuses on the effect of equivalence ratio (ER) on syngas composition and energy content.

2 GASIFICATION PLANT DESCRIPTION AND PROCESS SIMULATION

The gasification unit at the Spanish National Centre of Renewable Energies (CENER) is a pilot plant with a nominal power of 2 MW_{th} (Fig. 4), designed to operate with a wide range of biomass, with bulk densities ranging between 80 and 800 kg/m³ and moisture content below 30%. The integrated pilot is comprised of the following sub-systems: a) feeding system, b) atmospheric air-blown, atmospheric bubbling fluidized bed (ABFB) gasifier, c) syngas cleaning and discharge system and d) syngas combustion, flue gas cooling and cleaning system, accompanied by e) the distributed control system for remote and automatic operation (SCADA) and f) a micro-GC analyzer. The gasification experiments were conducted as follows: i) Start-up and heating of the ABFB gasifier and the combustion chamber with natural gas and heating of the pipeline system at ca. 250 °C through OK combustion, ii) air gasification of raw OK at nominal equivalence ratios (ER) between 0.20-0.30, iii) shutdown and cooling of the unit. All systems were cooled naturally, in order to avoid material damage due to high temperature gradients. The tests aimed at screening different ERs and recording the corresponding temperature profile in the gasifier (700-900 °C) as well as syngas quality. The latter was monitored in-line via a μ -GC. Tarry products composition was also measured during the tests, albeit their concentration was very low due to the use of a catalytically active bed material (i.e., bauxite). The various operational parameters and variables were also being monitored remotely and in real time via SCADA software. Various troubleshooting incidents were also addressed properly at the time of the experiments.

Figure 4: General view of the gasification pilot plant at CENER's facilities

The model used for the process simulation is illustrated in Fig. 5 [3]. The raw olive kernel is initially decomposed in a RYield reactor, where it is converted from a non-conventional solid to its elements (C(s), H₂, N₂, S, O₂, H₂O and ash). A stoichiometric reactor (RStoich) was used to estimate the methane production from solid char and hydrogen. The CH₄ flow and the decomposed biomass are then driven to a separator block, where a fraction of char, ash and methane are separated from the gas mixture entering to the gasifier (RGibbs reactor). In the last separator, fuel ash and the C(s) fraction that by-passed the RGibbs reactor are separated as solids from the mixture. Gasification temperature for all blocks was calculated as the average temperature of the thermocouples placed at the middle of the gasifier's bed zone.

Figure 5: Aspen Plus Model for ABFB Gasifier

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The necessary olive kernel quantity was provided by local suppliers and was stored on-site. Subsequently, OK fuel was characterized in terms of ultimate analysis, heating value, density and granulometry (particle size distribution) analyses (Tables 1 and 2). Typical values of Carbon, Oxygen and Hydrogen content were obtained in comparison to other olive kernel fuels [2]. Negligible quantities of Nitrogen, Sulfur and Chlorine were measured. The high moisture content of the as-received olive kernel is attributed to the absence of pre-drying. Finally, the OK Heating value lies on the mean value of other lignocellulosic biomass fuels [4–10].

Table I: Ultimate analysis of raw olive kernel biomass fuel

Ultimate Analysis (wt.%, db)				Immediate analysis (wt.%; wb)	analysis (wt.%; db)
C	O	H	N	H ₂ O	Ash ^{d.b.}
50.6	43.2	6	0.2	16.8	0.6

Table II: Heating value and density of raw olive kernel biomass fuel

LHV (MJ/kg) ^{w.b.}	HHV (MJ/kg) ^{w.b.}	Bulk density (kg/m ³) ^{w.b.}
15.3	16.7	730

The attempt to work on an E.R between 0.2 and 0.3 was not achievable due to technical issues. In specific, due to the high density of the OK (Table 2) the screw conveyor could only operate at its minimum capacity. As a result, the feed rate was fluctuating leading to a single average value of E.R around 0.3 ± 0.02 . Nonetheless, the unit could operate constantly for 12 hours with an average feeding rate of 600 kg/hr. The experimental results as well as the comparison with the simulation are presented below.

Figure 6 shows the average temperature of the gasification process along the height of the gasifier and at the outlet of the producer gas. Taking into consideration that both preheated air and olive kernel were inserted at the bottom of the reactor, the maximum temperature was observed in the bed zone due to combustion reactions and was equal to 834 °C. Isothermal conditions were established along the freeboard zone of the reactor.

Figure 6: Temperature profile of the gasifier

Fig. 7 presents the comparison between the model and the experimental results for ER equal to 0.3. As for the experimental results, CO₂ and H₂ contents were rather high and low, respectively compared to the relevant literature [11]. This could be possibly attributed to the combustion reaction as well as Water Gas-Shift (WGS) reaction as a result of the biomass feeding rate fluctuations. Nevertheless, a typical LHV syngas value for other olive residues fuels was obtained and was equal to 5 MJ/kg. Notably, negligible tar content was measured in the produced syngas, showcasing the effective tar cracking properties of the bauxite.

Also, it is mentioned that the plant is equipped with a chamber for the combustion of the produced syngas. Therefore, by considering the obtained syngas flow rate (1.48 tn/h) and LHV and by assuming a boiler efficiency of 0.85, the thermal output of the process can be estimated at around 1.6 MW_{th}, or 7 GWh_{th} for a continuous 6-month operation. This heat can be potentially used to cover the heating needs of ca. 700 households in the nearby village of Aoiz (2018 population of 2,624), effectively rendering the plant a dedicated biomass-fuelled district heating station.

For the simulation run, the composition of the biomass feedstock, the pressure and temperature values in the model reactors were modified according to the experimental data obtained from the experimental tests. It can be clearly illustrated that the model is capable of predicting the composition of syngas adequately in most cases (Fig. 7). CO₂ content is under-predicted, while the model results for H₂, CO, CH₄ and C₂H₄ content in syngas are validated by the experimental findings. Moreover, LHV values of the produced syngas did not reveal significant modifications for the experimental and the simulation results, respectively. The observed minor deviations can be attributed to both the unstable biomass flow rate due to olive kernel's high density and calorific value and the assumptions used for the model development.

Figure 7: Simulation vs Experimental results comparison

As mentioned above, the design of the existing feeding system along with the properties of olive kernel biomass fuel led to fluctuations in the feeding rate. For this reason, only the simulation model was used to predict the effect of ER in the quality of the produced syngas. Fig 8 shows a remarkable CO and H₂ rate decrease for higher air/biomass ratios. A rise in CO₂ molar fraction with ER increase is observed. With increasing ER, more active oxidation reactions will occur increasing the CO₂ concentration at the expense of CO and H₂. The LHV of dry gas notably decreased with increasing ER because of both the decreasing H₂ and CO contents and the enlarging dilution effect of nitrogen. The aforementioned results are in a good agreement with the literature [12].

Figure 8: Effect of ER on syngas composition and LHV

Biomass moisture influences both the LHV of the produced gas and efficiency of gasification. As the water associated with the biomass needs to be evaporated in the gasifier, high moisture feedstock increase the energy consumption in gasification. The evaporated water also reduces the lower heating value of the raw gas. High moisture feedstock may also cause technical challenges, such as blocking of the feeding systems [13]. Due to these adverse effects, drying of biomass to below 17 % via simple air-drying methods with no external heat requirements and its effect on syngas quantity and quality, is assessed next. Figure 9 presents the dependence of the syngas composition on the varying OK residual moisture content. The moisture level was varied over a realistic range for air-dried OK, above 3 %. It can be seen that rising moisture content slightly increased the H₂ and CO₂ concentration, whereas CO concentration decreased. This can presumably ascribed to the fact that higher moisture content favors the WGS and steam reforming reactions. The LHV value of syngas slightly decreased, from 5.3 to 5 MJ/kg to, because of the continuous decline of CO and increasing H₂O excess.

Figure 9: Effect of moisture content on syngas composition and LHV

For a constant E.R = 0.3, the effect of steam addition on a range of S/B ratios was next explored (Fig. 10). It can be seen that, H₂/CO ratio is substantially increased followed by a slight decline in LHV. Notably, with increasing S/B ratio, H₂ concentrations increased remarkably, while the CO concentration smoothly decreased. Steam injection could adjust the H₂/CO ratio of syngas by the combination of the water-gas reaction

($C+H_2O \rightleftharpoons CO+H_2, \Delta H = +131 \text{ KJ / mol}$) and WGS

reaction ($CO+H_2O \rightleftharpoons CO_2+H_2, \Delta H = -41 \text{ KJ / mol}$).

Increasing the amount of H₂O the above reactions shift toward the right and results in an increase of H₂ concentration and a decrease in CO concentration. As a result, H₂/CO ratio increases to values above 2.2, and the produced can be considered for downstream Fischer-Tropsch process [14]. The decrease in the LHV value could be attributed to the changes in syngas composition and yield.

Figure 10: Effect of steam addition on syngas composition

The use of enriched air via external pure oxygen provision is effective for reducing the nitrogen dilution effect and achieving higher heating value gas. Influence of oxygen percentage in the enriched air on the syngas composition and LHV is given in Figure 11. The H₂ concentration increased with rising OP from 15 % to 25 %, CO concentration showed a greater increment from 17 % to 37 %. CO₂ concentration first revealed the same trend with H₂ while CH₄ concentration showed a slight increase trend. With increasing oxygen content, the amount of nitrogen sent into the gasifier decreases gradually, causing changes in the initial concentration of reactants. The partial combustions are improved and more CO, CO₂, and H₂O are produced in the combustion section. A higher concentration of CO₂ and H₂O favors the forward Boudouard reaction and the water-gas reaction eventually leading to the increase of H₂ and CO concentration. The LHV value of syngas value increased greatly with increasing Oxygen Percentage and reached the maximum value of almost 10 MJ/kg. The aforementioned results indicate that oxygen-enriched air gasification favors the production of combustible gas components, including (H₂, CO, and CH₄) eventually producing a syngas as feedstock in gasification – SOFC combined cycles for heat and power generation [15].

Figure 11: Effect of feed oxygen content on syngas composition and LHV

4 CONCLUSIONS

A real-scale and bauxite-assisted olive kernel air BFB gasification was thoroughly examined in the present work at a 2 MW_{th} gasification plant in CENER Navarra Spain. Discontinuous feeding of biomass led to operation under an average value of E.R. = 0.30 ± 0.02 . Experimental results confirmed the beneficial role of bauxite towards complete tar elimination. The LHV of the produced syngas production was equal to 5.02 MJ/kg, and a thermal output of 1.62 MW_{th}. This heat can be potentially used to cover the heating needs of ca. 700 households in the nearby village of Aoiz effectively rendering the plant a dedicated biomass-fueled district heating station. Simulations were conducted in order to examine the potential operation of the plant under potential varying gasification conditions by using the same biomass feedstock. In specific, variations in key process parameters that can be implemented in the existing plant, namely E.R., residual OK moisture, S/B and O₂ content in the air exerted great impact on the syngas quality.

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